

D3.5

Public demand LEARNTECH 2030

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1 Introduction

This report is deliverable 3.5, which is part of milestone 6. It is connected to task 3.5 in WP 3 of the LEA project. The leader of the work package is Otto-von-Guericke-University, who also compiled this deliverable. The goal of task 3.5 is to identify the demand for future innovative procurement and the objective of this deliverable is to create demand policy recommendations. According to our grant agreement, this task is divided into two parts:

- 1) identify the demand within LEA for future PCP with focus to create a baseline of procurers needs for future innovative procurement work/preparations and in connection with WP 5 and the capacity building seminars as well as with WP 4 industrial global think tanks and future tools/venues for dialogue and
- 2) create a demand policy recommendation with focus to prepare the market for after LEA and until 2030 with recommendations on demand policy for the European education sector according to recommendations for the action plan “A stronger European Industry for Growth and Economic Recovery” (see [1]).

The first part can be found in chapter 4 and the second part in chapter 3. Innovative Procurement could be the solution to many questions and challenges schools, teachers and students will face in the future. Schools and school administration are rarely in the position to buy innovative technology, to train teachers and students how to use it for education and/or get the right infrastructure for the school to use technology.

To use the instrument of innovative procurement, the procuring organisations need information about the needs and demand for learning technologies at schools and in the education sector. This deliverable shall help them to get this information on a general level and in more detail for exemplary scenarios and it provides a toolkit of methodologies to conduct their own needs analysis investigation.

2 Methodology

A toolkit has been developed that procurers can use for the development of indicators and selection criteria for the identification of priorities within their demand for innovative procurement.

We have identified and tested several methodologies that can help procurers to gather the needs of the relevant stakeholders in education: schools, students, parents, teachers, school authorities.

2.1 Focus Group discussion

A focus group discussion (FGD) is a research tool to discuss a specific topic of interest. The group of participants is guided by a moderator who introduces topics for discussion and helps the group to participate in a lively and natural discussion amongst themselves.

The strength of FGD relies on allowing the participants to agree or disagree with each other so that it provides an insight into how a group thinks about an issue, about the range of opinions and ideas, and the inconsistencies and variation that exists in a particular community in terms of beliefs and their experiences and practices. A report should be prepared after the session is finished, summarising the session to reflect the opinions evenly and fairly.

A focus group is composed of 5 - 10 representatives of stakeholders, for the education sector this are mostly teachers, school administration, school authority, students and parents. It is recommended to involve all relevant parties, there might be other stakeholders like municipality, teachers unions etc. , but not to exceed the group size of 10 participants to enable an equal and fair discussion.

The beginning of the event was an anchor video in which all participants will be introduced to the topic. Subsequently, the group was separated into the relevant actors and a positioning on the three key questions was to be

created in micro-discussions. The individual positions on visions, challenges and goals of the school in 2030 were then presented and discussed in the entire focus group. The points mentioned will be recorded during the discussion and subsequently evaluated.

The evaluation of the results of the questionnaire and the evaluation of the focus group discussion is the first basis for answering the three key questions. The second basis is the comparison of these results with the forecasted challenges/goals/visions from the SDGs and the national and EU-wide digital agenda.

From the answers to three key questions, a guideline with recommendations for action for calls for innovative teaching and learning technology in schools emerges. This guide is intended to help schools meet future challenges with innovative technology.

2.2 The Balancing our Needs (BON) - Methodology

Users usually have difficulties with the level of needed quality and preparedness when participating in needs analysis processes. In the LEA Needs Analysis, we use Balancing Our Needs (BON) methodology. It starts with trends to assure that the needs analysis is future orientated enough. This way, sustainability (green footprint) is taken into account and it gives also an overview and inspiration of the theme.

When comparing different features of a product to be designed, you want to know which of these features are most important and relevant for the users and why. The goal of the BON workshop is to reveal these features of a PLE.

A BON workshop gives results in three categories. First you get the list of the most important features wanted in a PLE. From that list, we then create minimum requirements. These may be divided into minimum requirements in different countries. These results are the base for scenarios created to

enlighten and describe the desired workflow possible with a new and innovative PLE.

By using scenarios, we give to the suppliers a clear, but open vision about what is needed. Scenarios are highly usable in innovative procurement, because they are inspiring, but at the same time telling clearly with a concrete example, what the minimum requirements are. At the same time, it provides an effective tool for evaluating different alternatives.

The needs analysis workshops were designed by OU and OVGU. European procurer expert boards had a Balancing our Needs workshop in Halmstad in June 2018.

3 Demand Policy Recommendations

According to the EU Innovation Policies¹, demand-side innovation policies support and increase the uptake of innovations in society. Consumer confidence in innovative products, like the use of new technological solutions in classrooms, can be increased. These recommendations complement supply-side policy tools such as public funding schemes for educational procurement (such as these listed in D2.2).

1. Perform a Needs Analysis Workshop

Using one of the methodologies described, a needs analysis is important not only to get information about the actual needs in the area and the priorities of these needs, but also to involve especially schools and teachers from the very beginning. The success of ICT in schools lies in the hands of the teachers.

2. Establish a working infrastructure first

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/industry/innovation/policy/demand-side-policies_en

The technical infrastructure needs to work as reliably as the infrastructure for energy and water. A model of how this can look like has been described in deliverable D3.4 Basic Technical Infrastructure.

3. Offer Training and Support for Teachers

The uptake of ICT in schools depends on if and how teachers are using ICT tools in their everyday teaching. From the analysis of barriers and competencies in deliverable D3.2 we can see, that the lack of appropriate education and training opportunities is still a major barrier for teachers.

4. Standardization and Compliance

It is important to establish standards for the market to and on the demand side, to request products and services that respect these standards. The interoperability between digital components must be assured. In addition to technical standards, a standardisation in curricula is also important. That means that educational content becomes comparable in Europe. Students from other countries can get easier included into schools, when the gap between the knowledge that they already acquired in their home country and the content taught in the new school can be detected by comparing standardized curricula.

5. Easy Access to Information and Services

The access to digital content and services needs to be regulated in a form that it is easy to use by schools, teachers and students. This requires a copyright framework that allows access to content without legal barriers, regardless in which EU country the participant is located. It also requires an easy-to-use human-computer-interface for all age groups and skill levels.

3.1 UN Sustainable Development Goals

In “Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development” (see [3]), the United Nations formulated 17 sustainable development goals (SDG) to which the member states have committed themselves, both nationally and internationally. It is a call for action for all countries to

implement measures to achieve these goals and targets by the year 2030. The SDGs address global challenges and aim to be “a blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all”([3]). SDG 4 in particular addresses quality education. This includes the following aims (among others):

- a complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education
- access for all women and men to affordable and quality technical, vocational and tertiary education
- eliminate gender disparities in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education

The monitoring of SDG 4 in an EU context focuses on basic education, tertiary education and adult learning and is described in a statistical article at eurostat (see SDG 4 Quality Education, EU 2019, [4]). As can be seen in table 1, the EU has made significant progress in increasing participation in basic and tertiary education, but progress in adult learning has been much slower, and the percentage of underachievers in the PISA test is worse for the past 5 years.

Indicator	Long-term trend (past 15 years)	Short-term trend (past 5 years)
Basic education		
🎯 Early leavers from education and training	↑	↗
🎯 Participation in early childhood education	↑	↑
🎯 Underachievement in reading, maths and science	↓ ⁽¹⁾	↓ ⁽²⁾
Young people neither in employment nor in education and training (*)	↑	↑
Tertiary education		
🎯 Tertiary educational attainment	↑	↑
🎯 Employment rate of recent graduates	↑ ⁽³⁾	↑
Adult education		
🎯 Adult participation in learning	↓	↓

(*) Multi-purpose indicator.

(¹) Trend for 'reading performance' only.

(²) Past 6-year period.

(³) Past 12-year period.

Table 1: Indicators measuring progress towards SDG 4, EU-28

Symbol	With quantitative target	Without quantitative target
	Trends for indicators marked with this 'target' symbol are calculated against an official and quantified EU policy target. In this case the arrow symbols should be interpreted according to the left-hand column below. Trends for all other indicators should be interpreted according to the right-hand column below.	
	Significant progress towards the EU target	Significant progress towards SD objectives
	Moderate progress towards the EU target	Moderate progress towards SD objectives
	Insufficient progress towards the EU target	Moderate movement away from SD objectives
	Movement away from the EU target	Significant movement away from SD objectives
:	Calculation of trend not possible (for example) time series too short)	

Note: The two methods for calculating progress used in this report are explained in more detail in the introduction and in the annex; for an overview of the considered policy targets see Table II.18 in the annex.

Table 2: Explanation of symbols for indicating progress towards SDG objectives and targets

Several key trends for the EU have been identified in the statistical analysis, both positive and negative, where the challenges for the next years can be derived from:

- Early leaving from education and training has reduced significantly since 2002, but progress has stagnated over the past few years
- Despite improved participation rates, education outcomes in reading, maths and science have deteriorated
- Early leavers and low-educated young people face particularly severe problems in the labour market
- Foreign-born residents achieve lower tertiary attainment rates and lower recent graduate employment rates

Following the indicators established by the EC, it can be seen that decreased learning results (underachievement in reading, math and science) are the central challenge in an age of rapid digital change. There are roots to tackle like;

- traditional and closed education systems
- lack of alignment between real educational needs and offered technology
- teachers experienced resistance to new technology

3.2 Digital Agenda

The “Digital Agenda for Europe” ([5]) aims to “*deliver sustainable economic and social benefits from a digital single market based on fast and ultra fast internet and interoperable applications.*” This requires an ongoing level of commitment at EU and member state levels and needs to be adapted into national agendas.

One of the action areas is “Enhancing digital literacy, skills and inclusion”, which clearly corresponds with the use of ICT technology in education. The digital skills necessary for innovation and growth needs to be increased and upgraded and the attractiveness of the ICT sector should be improved for young people. The actions defined by the EC include the proposition of digital literacy and competences as a priority for the European Social Fund until 2020 and the development of tools to identify and recognise the competences of ICT practitioners and users. All member states shall, for example, implement long-term e-skills and digital literacy policies and mainstream eLearning in national policies. In the case of Germany, there is a national agenda, and several federal states have adopted it as well.

Because ICT is no longer a specific sector but the foundation of all modern innovative economic systems, and in order to ensure a fair, open and

secure digital environment, the Commission has developed the “ Digital Single Market Strategy”(see [9]). It is based on three pillars: providing better access for consumers and businesses to digital goods and services across Europe, creating the right conditions for digital networks and services to flourish, and maximising the growth potential of the digital economy.

The access to digital content is a foundation for the successful use of ICT in education. A modern european copyright framework for e.g. learning materials that can be used across borders is important to create a better market for suppliers and in this way provide a greater variety of resources for schools, teachers and students.

3.3 BOHEMIA study

The BOHEMIA study is the main EU foresight study and describes perspectives for the European Union’s future research and innovation policies (see [6]). One of the target scenarios of the report is scenario 19 “Towards a New Knowledge System”, with a top priority of “adapting educational techniques to online environments, and piloting various solutions (e.g., distributed online courses with tutoring, navigating through the stock of knowledge). For each scenario, there are aspirations and visions formulated that are aims for the future. For scenario 19, it says:

“It is now 2040 ... ubiquitous digitalisation has transformed science, technology, research and education to a new integrated knowledge system. Abundant data, real-time and historical, are easily accessible through AI devices. Education makes extensive use of the digital tools. It empowers young and older people to make effective use of data, information and knowledge for social and economic ends. As knowledge becomes pervasive people lead more productive fulfilling lives. But established institutions are challenged to adapt. “

The Delphi survey conducted within the study collected statements on

developments in the area of education (see [7]) combined with an estimated time of realisation. Among these statements are the following:

- more than 50% of European universities offer open learning platforms free of charge
- virtual reality and augmented reality techniques are standard practice in 95% of all educational settings
- educational systems in the EU give equal weight to competitive and collaborative learning practices
- more than 50% of all publicly funded schools in the EU have replaced the conventional disciplinary teaching methods with a problem-solving pedagogy and curricula

The targeted scenario 19 has been described in detail in its own report (see [8]), which contains recommendations for future directions for EU R&I policy. It summarises that by 2040, the ubiquitous digitalisation has transformed science, technology, research and education to a new integrated knowledge system. Abundant data, real-time and historical, will be easily accessible through AI devices and education will make extensive use of the digital tools. But while these developments will empower people to make effective use of data, established institutions will be challenged to adapt.

But nevertheless, the open, collaborative knowledge system promises to be an important contributor to the European society and economy.

4 Results from FGP

For the development of the recommendation for future innovative procurements it is not only necessary to ask about possible challenges, but also about potential solutions with regard to innovative learning technologies. To learn about this, the relevant stakeholders should come together to express and discuss their needs. For the discussion to identify

the demand in LEA, the methodology of focus groups has been chosen. OvGU and Oulu with support from other partners prepared a guideline and other material to support the discussion.

The following key questions have been identified to get the thoughts and ideas of the participants about learning technologies:

1. What are the technological visions for the school in 2030?
2. What are the main challenges to take on/ solve until 2030?
3. What are the goals for schools in 2030?

The focus group and the survey are developed in relation to these questions. In this chapter, the results of the focus group discussion and the survey are presented, together with the findings from researching additional resources.

4.1 Focus Group Discussions within LEA

A focus group discussion (FGD) is defined as “a tool to discuss a specific topic of interest with a group of participants. It is guided by a moderator who introduces topics for discussion and helps the group to participate in a lively and natural discussion amongst themselves. “. (see [2])

For LEA, the focus groups should consist of 5 to 10 participants from the following groups: teachers, ICT personnel, principals, teachers, students, education policy makers and procurers. Not every group needed to be represented.

In addition, a moderator was needed to facilitate the discussion and to make sure that all groups participate evenly in the discussion and the focus is on the key questions.

During October 2019, each procurer of the LEA project invited 5 - 10 participants, and conducted a focus group discussion on the topic “Envisioning Public Demand LEARNTECH 2030”. At the beginning, the participants watched a video for inspiration and got the three key

questions presented. Then they got together in groups according to their roles and discuss shortly the videos, take positions and fill out the table provided. This could be done in any language, but needed to be translated into English afterwards. After about 10 minutes, or when they think they are done, the whole group got together again and participants presented their positions, e.g. presenting their tables to the group and discuss it.

The procurers took up the role of the moderator, accompanied by a minute-taker, to write down what was mentioned by the participants during the discussion. In addition, keywords and key points have been collected in templates provided by the organisers.

The templates from all the groups (Finland, Italy, Portugal, Spain and Germany) have then been collected afterwards and evaluated by OvGU. The key points from these answers have been organised in relation to the three key questions and categories have been identified. These categories can be weighted and ranked by the number of assigned key points and aspects. Building on this, the procurers can make an initial thematic or content-related delimitation for the planned call. The categories are:

Category	Visions	Challenges	Goals
Hardware and Software	x	x	x
Acceptance of Learning/ Teaching systems	x		
Learning/ Teaching assistance	x		
Social Issues		x	x
Teacher		x	x
Pedagogical		x	x
Connecting to the world	x		

Room to learn/teach	x		
(Infra-) Structure		x	x
Learning Process	x		
Student			x
School			x

The category "Hardware and Software" could be identified during the evaluation of the protocols of the FDGs for each key question. This summarizes all aspects related to concrete school hardware and software components (e.g. student end devices, compatible software). The category "(infra-)Structure" (identified in key question 2: challenges and 3: visions) differs from this by considering aspects of the elementary supply of schools with WLAN, for example. The category "Social issues" contains discussion points for society as a whole, the category "Teachers" contains discussion points for teachers. The category "Pedagogical", on the other hand, includes aspects that are not directly attributable to the teacher, but to pedagogical work as such.

The frequency of answers for certain categories are shown in figures 1 to 3. The weight of the categories was determined by the number of assigned aspects as a percentage. Appendix 1 contains detailed tables with the categories and all the aspects mentioned.

Figure 1: Relative frequencies of categories for key question: What are the technological visions for the school in 2030?

Figure 2: Relative frequencies of categories for key question: What are the main challenges to take on/ solve until 2030?

Figure 3: Relative frequencies of categories for key question: What are the goals for schools in 2030?

The results of the discussions show that the FGD generates target-oriented reflections on the 3 key questions. The participants expressed good ideas and visions for schools, which are used as a basis for tendering processes. In particular, there was a certain similarity in the responses of the different partners. The participants expressed support for the setting in order to have an open discussion.

4.2 Survey for LEA focus groups

The survey has been presented at the end of the discussion. It consists of two ranking tasks and three questions, where the participants should finish a given sentence.

For the survey 66 records were collected (24 teachers, 13 procurer & school administrators, 11 education policy makers). 14 participants did not specify their profession.

In the first two questions, the participants were asked to sort phrases according to their perceived importance. The ranked answers were then weighed by their rank and summed. Figures 1 and 2 show the highest ranked answers for each question.

Question 1: What challenges will education face in 2030? Please rank the listed challenges.

1. Not enough financial resources in schools
2. No teacher training about how to use new technologies
3. Shortage of teachers
4. Missing equipment for students
5. Not enough infrastructure in schools

Fig. 1: 5 highest ranked answers for question 1

Question 2: What content from the SDG's will be very important for teachers and students in 2030?²

1. Quality Education
2. Climate Action
3. Responsible Consumption and Production
4. Affordable and Clean Energy
5. Decent Work and Economic

Fig. 2: 5 highest ranked answers for question 2

² With question 2 participants received a link to the SDG's.

For the following questions, the participants had to complete a sentence either with one of the presented answers or with their own words. The results are shown in figures 3 to 6.

Fig. 3: distribution of absolute frequencies of answers to question 3

Question 4: Please complete the following sentence:
Learning will be facilitated in 2030 by...

Fig. 4: distribution of absolute frequencies of answers to question 4

Fig. 5: distribution of absolute frequencies of answers to question 5

Fig. 6: distribution of absolute frequencies of answers to question 6

The results from the ranking in question 1 highly correspond with the results of the focus group discussion regarding the current challenges.

Especially the highest ranked issue “not enough financial resources for schools” has been mentioned in several forms like “economic barriers” or “monetary resources” (see challenges categorie “(Infra-)Structures” in Annex 1). This is similar for the challenges in teacher training (“teachers have to handle the new technology”)and teacher shortage. The ranking also shows the importance of infrastructural problems (see figure 2 in 2.1).

The variety of answers to questions 3 to 6 is also in accordance to the topics discussed in the focus group discussion. The fact, that the open answer (“other”) hasn’t been chosen, indicates that the provided answers are covering the relevant issues.

5 Conclusions

This report focused on outlining the demand policy for future innovative procurement recommendations. Focus groups were used to identify challenges, goals and visions for school in 2030. First, focus group discussions with LEA were conducted.

Conclusions for technological, pedagogical and administrative measures can be summarized according to visions, challenges and goals:

Technological	
Visions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Implementation of AR and VR in schools ● Innovative devices designed for school usage
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Operational safety of current infrastructure (Fear of mistakes/ malfunction, technology that doesn't work) ● inconsistent architectures
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expansion of wireless connectivity ● Easy to use Hard- & Software (important that technology is "self-explanatory")

Pedagogical	
Visions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AI that can support and assist students at the individual level ● Enabling distance education
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of teacher education regarding the handling of innovative technologies ● Increased administrative tasks for teachers

Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology to match the needs of all users in school • Technology supports practical teaching and learning (learning by doing, lifelong learning, ...)
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Administrative	
Visions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection to the world (easy exchange between schools, classes, students, teachers, ...) • Fully accepted use of technology in education (e.g. technology is part of all the different types of teaching materials)
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unfitting laws and regulations on integrity and openness for school development • Legislation is not given an opportunity to follow the rapid development that will take place
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher accessibility of technology (especially WiFi connection) • Enable equal education for all

According to the survey for LEA focus groups, the biggest challenges for future education include lack of both financial resources and teacher training to use new technologies. Quality education and climate action, in turn, were identified as the most important content from the SDG's for teachers and students. In regards to teaching, digital and personal learning systems for every student were viewed as the most likely outcome for education in 2030, as contrasted with technical learning or teaching aids in the case of learning. Additionally, the participants evaluated that

administrative work would be facilitated by digital administration systems, while teacher training was mostly viewed to be facilitated by virtual training schools, technical teaching or learning aids and virtual coaches.

According to earlier research and action plans presented in this report, it is clear that there is a need for providing affordable and equitable education as well as enhancing people's digital literacy and ICT related skills. Additionally, it is important to ensure digital accessibility of services. Once the scenarios for future educational technologies are contrasted with focus group related data, however, it can be established that current views on the capabilities of future technology as well as its adaptability to educational settings varies between different stakeholders. Nevertheless, through identifying barriers alongside with potential and pursuable benefits associated with the use of educational technology, there is a chance to embrace the future of technology in a practical and meaningful way.

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Annexes

Annex 1: Detailed results of the FDG

What are the *technological visions* for the school in 2030?

Categorie	Examples
Connecting to the world	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visiting classes all over the world virtually - Teaching and learning everywhere but with interaction with others - Technology based on being connected to the internet - AR and VR shrink the world - Opportunity to learn from other parts of the world - Distance education is more common - Exchange between schools (all over the world) - Exchange between schools becomes normal - exchange between teachers
Learning Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Miniature Computer with a Pen with connection to the brain - Students equipment is individually tailored - How we learn best and how we can stimulate everyone regardless of their level to reach their full potential - The focus on the individual's development will be strengthened - teacher as learning coach - innovative learning/ teaching with ICT
Hardware + Software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AR + Reality are mixed in classrooms - A desk with a build in tablet - Holograms - video recording of lessons - mobile working stations - robotic - AR boards and VR-Kits - Today unknown technology based on VR and AI - VR in schools/ lessons
Acceptance of Learning/ Teaching systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stop seeing technology as something that is outside the teaching materials - Technology is part of all the different types of teaching materials that will be in the future (technology is a simply part of learning) - Everything that the school uses should be seen as "resources for learning" and not divided into different categories - Range of available teaching resources is considerably larger - Publicly controlled system

Learning/ Teaching assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI learning/ teaching assistant - Holograms as pedagogical solutions - Robots that can support and assist students at the individual level - Routine tasks are automated - Mechanical summative assessment - Button to activate a virtual teacher (on a computer or another tool) - Virtual Teacher that assist the teachers in the education and also assist the students (individual learning, show sth. again, ...) - Avatar support/ assist the teachers - E-learning supports individual learning
Room to learn/ teach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Classroom is not more important, but the school is a very important place for social interaction and inspiration - Distance education is more common - Using VR/AR daily

What are the main *challenges* to take on/ solve until 2030?

Categorie	Examples
(Infra-) Structural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Money - Students gain access to devices regardless of social status - Timelines - Everything is wireless and easy to use - Similar possibilities everywhere - Not enough time for the digital transformation - Are schools able to afford technology like smart technical tools, voice control and robots? - Legislation and the economy for schools - Economic barriers (not enough money given for schools) - Enough resources to train teachers and school staff -> high level - Laws and regulations on integrity and openness help schools to be shaped into the modern educational place it is expected to be - Monetary resources and the ability to rely on those who want to go first and constantly learn new things - Legislation is given an opportunity to follow the rapid development that will take place - Open access funds - Inclusion - Devices have to be available
Hardware + Software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Keeping up with the technological development - Problems with hardware/ connection - Technology that don't work - Fear of mistakes/ malfunction - Architectural barriers - Functional illiteracy - Data security - Malfunction - Too many different devices in the classroom
Social issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Corporate responsibility - Everyone needs access - Democratic deficit (important for the connection all over the world) - Creating an understanding, that technology should be a natural and natural part of the school (way of thinking) - Acceptance of innovative digital teaching/ learning tools

Teacher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teacher education - Lack of teacher - Teachers have to handle the new technology - Teacher inability to join the digital transformation - Increase the administrative tasks for teachers - Teachers need the knowledge and willingness to use the new technology
Pedagogical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How technology supports learning and pedagogy at its best - How games, VR, AR and holograms are used to help the students to learn instead of just playing with them - Focus on learning - Search for indicators that meet the needs of children (students) - Students use devices/ technology to solve problems, but not to understand the process (like cheating) - Didactic approaches - Research and Development: Curriculum - Mix between VR and reality

What are the goals for schools in 2030?

Categorie	Examples
(Infra-) Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Budget problems fixed with corporate sponsors - Everything should be wireless - Technology has to be accessible - Create innovative environments - Same infrastructure and resources for all schools
Hardware + Software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has to be adapted to the individual - Important that technology is "self-explanatory" - Technology is not an exclusionary barrier to good school environment - Support the "classic tools of learning" - Match the needs of all students - become more ecological with technology
Social issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equal education for all - Technology doesn't replace social interaction (don't replace the actual social contact and other living people in real life) - Less prejudism (in the context of using technology in school) - Everyone should be open minded for using technology in school - Think big and have a clear awareness and heart when it comes to learning
Teacher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers are all educated to use technology - Technology solve the lack of teachers - Teacher as facilitator - Teacher perceived as a guide to boost the creativity of students
Student	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learn with the help of technology - Solution for dropouts (Education on distance) - Reduce dropouts -> Individual Learning - Learning type-oriented lessons
School	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focus on being there for students - Inspire the lifelong learning - Technology is used adequately (guarantee the possibility of lifelong learning) - Reduces administration - Time in school is used as efficiently as possible - Schools work together with the rest of the community (public and private) - The entire school works from the point of view of reaching every student based on their condition - Remain independent despite the use of technology
Pedagogical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning by doing - Inspire the lifelong learning - Understanding that the learning process is a lifelong process and that technology is an integral part of this - No distinguish between teaching materials and technology - Physical space in school change -> whole school - Practical teaching - Sustainable didactic tools

